

Analysis of Centripetal Nationalism In Contest Winners Novel of “Seberapa Indonesiakah Dirimu?” by Candra Rahma

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Abstract

The purpose of the paper analysis is to describe the direction narrated nationalism in three winning novels Competition “Seberapa Indonesiakah dirimu?”. Research results in this showing that 1) all three novels describe a construction nation community with awareness collective in the form of history, customs, and resources nature; 2) a construction nation contains problematization. Nation by faint split up in room traditional and modern which resulted in inequality social; and 3) By whole the three novels want integration locality in nationalism with so direction nationalism narrated in the three novels are nationalism centripetal. Direction nationalism centripetal believed Becomes solution in overcome problematization nationality.

Keywords: *community imagined, nation, nationalism centripetal, consciousness collective*

INTRODUCTION

The 2014 year, the publisher book the national. Three A series, held a contest for youth novel writing with the title contest "Seberapa Indonesiakah dirimu?" be chosen three creation the best, namely the novel Because of Me, not Blind creation Ready Kuswanto lined up Becomes champion first, then followed by the novel Kaki Langit Talumae creation Vishnu Mahendra, and the novel How to Love Indonesia by Duma M. Sembiring. The three novels load draft nation and nationalism promoted by the author at a time implies orientation organizer.

There are four reasons behind the interested researcher in the third creation winner contest. First, Indonesia as well as post-colonial countries other have pa roble with nation-states and nationalism. This thing looks from often conflicts in the name of the nation-state and nationalism. The conflict is not free from the development of understanding public against nation-states and nationalism.

METHOD

This study of analysis uses a descriptive qualitative method because it explains a social event for how the writer uses for analyzing the paper. This method is seen by the writer to be very important because this method will show a form of explanation related to a phenomenon that is interpreted in the context and concept of writing. Of course, in carrying out this research, the author uses a hermeneutic approach because this paper analysis will be studied by exegesis of the contents and adjusting to the events that occurred at that time. The research data is in the form of words, phrases, sentences, or paragraphs that contain the author's description of Indonesia. The results of this description are used to analyze the tendency of forms of nationalism.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The findings in this study are the three novels imply the trend shape or direction of nationalism. Trend the in the form of nationalism Indonesian people who return to inheritance culture traditionally. A culture is a traditional place as Foundation's constructing identity self perform public state. Identity self-based on culture traditional then Becomes a differentiator between " us " and " them ".

The three novels also narrate how inheritance history and tradition. After the tradition that composes conception of nation, the shared to members then will occur relation social between member awareness of relation this is what then meant with awareness collective. The awareness of the growing togetherness and bonds that lead to community imagined. This thing will impact on the existence of at alone one This is what it is thick carried by a third d the author

The purpose of this analysis of papers in the form of discussions a provides offer solutions related to the problem construction of nation and nationalism. The three novels raised story opposition Among villages and cities between tradition and modernity. The village and population always depict groups experiencing oppression or injustice.

Besides the three winning novels, the contest also presents narration construction natio. Nation depicted as member community members feel there in the fo similar larity history and tradition. History and tradition should be generations on as livelihood existence action. Understanding the action at a time Becomes an identity self member nation and nation that one, as well as a differentiator between nations. Bond and love this is what becomes Foundation nationalism.

CONCLUSION

From how the writer subjectively sees the paper analysis that talks about nationalism no could be released from construction nation. Of the three novels as research data sources showing that construction nation owns relation with formation nationalism. Construction nation related with conception identity self-relationship social and differentiator intercommunity / group Construction

identity nation this based on awareness collective. Awareness collective this a sense of ownership on similarity history custom customs and resources nature. Construction nation that has built no as well as immediately make unity inside it turns out cause problem. Nation by faint split up in room traditional and modern which resulted in inequality social. The three novels are so clear and describe inequality social modern and traditional society with put the traditional lower than the modern. The three novels tend to describe life public traditional Becomes a solution in overcome problems in action in modern times. When the three novels want integration locality in nationalism. Shape narrated nationalism centripetal.

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